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Gender equality human rights and sustainable development goals

Dr. Saher Hussain and Dr. Hajra Masood

Abstract

For a sustainable development, it's crucial to end all discrimination against women and girl not only as a basic human right; positive impact on economic growth and development of any country is noticed by empowering women and girls. Taking gender equality as its most important task UNDP has shown that remarkable changes in past two decades there are more girls in school in comparison to last 15 years; to achieve parity between primary education of girls and boys many regions are making their efforts.

Keywords: Gender equality and sustainable development

Introduction

For a peaceful prosperous and a sustainable world, fundamental human right that is gender equality is necessary. One of the most pervasive forms of discrimination in all the developmental process is gender inequality. Anyone can be affected by gender inequality, but it has a major impending effect on the global progress towards achieving sustainable development, as second class gender women face the most discrimination. Among the eight millennium development goals gender equality and women's empowerment is the third, which has all its emphasis on the sustainable development along with other aspects of growth. To achieve the sustainable development aspect gender equality is an essential rather than an instrumental goal. Rather than as a mechanism for achieving other goal its explicitly cherished as an end in itself. Gender equality is its own development goal which is reflected in 45 targets and 54 gender specific indicators of sustainable development goals. To create a multiplier effect across all of sustainable development goal, closing the gender gap is the first step. For a sustainable development, it's crucial to end all discrimination against women and girl not only as a basic human right; positive impact on economic growth and development of any country is noticed by empowering women and girls. Taking gender equality as its most important task UNDP has shown that remarkable changes in past two decades there are more girls in school in comparison to last 15 years; to achieve parity between primary education of girls and boys many regions are making their efforts. Although there are more and more women workforce in the market there is still a white gap in the income of both genders still exist which is 76% for women and 49% men, almost 35% of women have been sexually exploited once in their lifetime, discrimination in public offices along with the 23% pay of gap, in addition to difference in holding of ownership of agricultural land which is 12.8% for women and 80 7.8% for men an equal division of unpaid care and domestic work is one of the major causes of huge burden on women who spend 18% of their they time in comparison to 7% of men's time in their work on the other hand climate change disasters, regional conflict and migration continue to have a disproportionate effect on women and children. Last but not the least women hold 24% of parliament seat globally in comparison to 76% of men globally. For establishment of a peaceful prosperous and sustainable world gender equality as a fundamental human right is necessary. Unfortunately, at the current time, one in five women and girls between the age of 15 to 49 have reported experiencing physical or sexual violence by an intimate partner within a 12 month period and 49 countries currently have no laws protecting women's from domestic violence. Practices such as child marriage and FGM (female genital multination) has been declined by 30% in the past decade, to completely eliminate such practice, still much work is to be done. It is very vital to give women equal rights over land and property, sexual and reproductive health, and to technological development. To achieve greater gender equality more and more women leaders are needed and presently we have more women working in public office than ever before.

Agenda of 2030 and the sustainable development goal highlight that empowerment of women and equality are integral part for achievement of sustainable development. Focusing on targets like poverty reduction, work, agricultural productivity, Hunger, health and nutrition, water and sanitation climate change related planning, participation in public life and sustainable cities and communities. Gaps are to be eliminated to have multidimensional effect on gender equality, women empowerment and sustainable development. For example, if women had the same access to productive resources as men, they could increase yield on the farms by 20 to 30%, which could raise total agricultural put in developing countries by 2.524% per annum, and reduce the number of hungry people in the world by 12 to 17%. According to an analysis of 182 peace agreements, when women participate as witnesses, signatories, mediators and negotiators, resulting agreements are 35% more likely to last at least 15 years. According to UNDP estimates, to achieve gender equality in educational attainment and in labour force participation by 2030 can raise global gross domestic product by 4.4 trillion dollars or 3.6 % and reduce the share of global population living in extreme poverty (\$1.90 a day) by 0.5% points (Dugarova E., 2018) [4].

UNDP approach to gender mainstreaming:-

Human rights: UNDP will ensure that

1. Research and analysis of gaps is based on program design which realises human rights of men and women.
2. Phases of program cycle apply human rights principle and standards.
3. Situation analysis, performance monitoring and reporting explicitly document progress in achieving gender equality, in line with the the principles and standards of Beijing platform for action, convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women.

Women and men and as equal participants for change: when all people have opportunities to achieve their aspiration and fulfil their potential then only the idea of sustainable development goal can be achieved. It views all women and men as an active agent of change and thus focuses on ensuring that those who are left behind are empowered and guided through the proper agencies for making decisions in their life and participate in the development process of society. As such interventions are supported by UNDP will go beyond counting numbers of beneficiaries by gender and will focus on empowering and creating agency for women and men for further closing the gender gap.

Leaving no one behind: commitment to support partners to address multiple and intersecting forms of discrimination, such as those based on poverty, geographic location, identity , race ,religion disability and other characteristics are the objective of UNDP.

Leaving no one behind and reaching the furthest behind first requires improving capacities to analyse and target populations affected by multiple forms of discrimination.

Transforming gender and power relation: this objective acknowledges that for achieving gender equality and sustainable development transforming gender and power relation is will pursue initiatives that accelerate structural transformation for gender equality and remove the institutional, societal, political and legal barriers hindering its achievement. This includes working with partners to address the root cause of gender inequalities and change the

discriminatory social norms, attitudes and practice that deny women and girls right and opportunities. Engaging men and boys: an important aspect of this objective is in pattern with ' he or she' men and boys both as Allies in closing gender gaps and in empowering women and girls but also to address discriminatory attitudes and practice and oppressive forms of masculinity that impact both women and men is an engaging move done by United Nations global solidarity movement for gender equality.

This is particularly important in preventing and responding to all forms of gender based violence as well as addressing the unequal distribution of rose and opportunities of women, men girls and boys, both at home and in public sphere. Approaches can include public awareness campaigns showcasing positive masculinities, such as benefits of men's engagement in caregiving and enhancing capacities of men and boys for inclusive engagements at household, community and policy level, across different sectors and generations.

Contextualization: recognising that UNDP works in partnership with governments and in a variety of country context, UNDP will follow a contextualized and country driven approach, with its primary role to contribute for regional integrated platforms to address challenges requiring multispectral responses including discriminatory norms and standards and to mobilize partnerships across the United Nations system to support country specific efforts to advance gender equality and women's empowerment in the context of achieving 2030 agenda. Innovation: one of the critical aspect of gender equality work is innovation. Advancing gender equality calls for innovative approaches from community efforts to behaviour change campaigns to challenge discriminatory social norms and practices that major part of gender inequality. Technological innovations from mobile banking application to new clean energy, eliminate structural and societal barriers that prevent women from accessing financial and other services and break traditional patriarchal supply chain of information, resources and power. Participation, decision making and management roles of women are critical to all the above discussed approaches for the gender equality and sustainable development processes and also partition of local, National and international level of governments, where they can be effective agents of change. We can very well observed that developed countries women have a sense of going to lifestyle and consumption pattern seems to be more concerned about the environment and have a greater sense of responsibility towards achieving sustainable development. Women's are responsible consumer of environment and therefore are likely to recycle and use public transportation more often than men. There need to be taken measure to ensure that participation of women is fully in the discussion on economic development, social progress and environmental protection and management, including in the plan and implementation of adoption and measures to elevate climate change. Recent study says about representation at board for top management level, women are more strong than those that perform better, suggestive of that increase number of women in leadership and decision making position can generate a greater diversity of green solution and contribute more in effective sustainable development. Participatory processes that involve end users of technology-men and women at the household and community levels-help ensure that technologies are

developed to contribute in gender equality and women's empowerment as its main point of view. However, women's lack of all limited access to resources such as land, clean water and affordable energy, hinders their full participation in a green economy, and puts them at a greater risk in times of natural disasters. So called women's spokes platforms have proved to be useful for AIIMS for engaging women's organisation with governments and other stakeholders at both National and international levels.(United Nations, 2017).

Women's and girls' access to education, training, skill and capacity building holds the key to their empowerment and improved livelihood. Eco space and opportunity should be given to women in science and technology field so that they can play a stronger role in research and development on environmentally safe. Government collaboration with academician and civil society E should work for redesigning educational curriculum and teaching material so as to address current challenges of environment and its thread post buy climate change and its impact on women and men. Training in vocation can help to ensure women's and girls in hands knowledge, skills and capacity in installation, use and repair of green technologies and systems. This gives would not only contribute towards enhancing women's opportunity to find decent work and full employment but also open up new entrepreneurial opportunities for them. An important tool which is microfinance is important for promoting women's economic empowerment particularly if it goes hand in hand with the growth plan designed to prevent women from falling into unmanageable debt patterns.

This would require improved assessment, monitoring and evaluation mechanism of microfinance provisions. Women's community-based and grassroots initiatives in the green economy have the potential if introduced in large scale; it would contribute significantly to word sustainable development. This requires the ongoing promotion of women's initiatives by enhancing their access to economic, financial and environmental resources these initiatives to make effective it should be linked to a supported by holistic, multispectral and participatory national planning, policy and budget frameworks.

Large number of initiatives from institutional mechanism, legislative provisions, plans; policies and programs has been taken for the promotion of gender equality and sustainable development. Key challenges that needs to be address at the institutional level includes creating a common understanding among the government agencies for importance of women's participation in green economy, and tackling the impact of vested interest in some key environmental resources and services related areas. Gender responsive budgeting can help ensure more equitable and effective resources allocation and would further contribute for distributional outcomes that favour gender equality. Working closely across the United Nations system most notably with UN women to support countries to achieve sustainable development is the commitment done by UNDP. To make gender equality a reality, it's necessary that basic human rights should be given for sustainable world, it's a commitment done by UNDP.

Women's empowerment and gender equality are vital to achieve 2030 agenda for sustainable development which envisions a world "of universal respect for human rights and human dignity" in which "every woman and girl enjoys full

gender equality and all legal, social and economic barriers to their empowerment have been removed".

2018 to 2021 strategy of UN dip for gender equality is the third search strategy which provides a road map to integrate and elevate gender equality into all aspects of UNDP's work to reduce poverty, build resilience and achieve peace in communities and territories, helping to accelerate progress towards the 2030 agenda. In particular, the strategy delineates the undo commitment to: (UNDP: 2018) ^[8].

Strengthen UNDP interventions tackling structural change that accelerates gender equality and women's empowerment; Strengthen the integration of gender equality into UNDP's work on the environment energy and crisis response and recovery; Better align you nap programming with the centrality of gender equality and women's empowerment to achievement of sustainable development; and Bhind Pawan institutional mechanism for gender mainstreaming such as gender equality seal and gender market which provides measurable standards and incentive to drive development progress.

There are more sustainable development goals apart from these which have to equally contribute for gender equality. Human Settlements in cities should be inclusive of safety measures for both genders, children and old age people, it should be resilient towards sustainable development instead of disasters such as flood, droughts, storm kills more women than men because of structural inequalities in the society for example unable to take a bus tour clinic to deliver a child can result in permanent disability or death of a women. Urgent action is to be taken to combat the gender inequality and its impacts as already discussed in article earlier women spend increasingly long as hunting for food, fuel and water, all struggling to grow crops. When disasters strike, women are more likely to Perish. Women with their experience and traditional knowledge can offer valuable insight into better managing the climate and its risk. They also have a right to protect themselves and to participate in decisions taken for the sustainable development.

Further few of the cases studies are being discussed to show how gender equality will help us to come over the vicious cycle of poverty and under development. It's a program taken up by Asian development bank's rural connectivity investment program in five states: Assam, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha and West Bengal. It has also helped advance development goals intrinsic to sustainable and inclusive growth. (Asian Development Bank: Report).

Afghanistan is one of the poorest countries in the world. 11 million Afghans or 36% of the population live in absolute poverty. Around 7 million Afghans are classed as food insecure, consuming less than 2,100 kilo-calories per day. Widows, of which there are said to be around 1.5 million in this war-torn country are especially disadvantaged with few options for them to earn an income and support themselves. Australian-based non-profit organisations Mahboba's Promise and Food Ladder launched a collaborative social enterprise project addressing food security of vulnerable women and their families in Afghanistan. Food Ladder addresses food security by empowering the poorest people in the world with its environmentally sustainable, high-yield, hydroponic greenhouse garden system. This system derives from commercial farming techniques, delivering commercial-scale quality and output to the poor. The aim of this project is to create a local source of food to communities and the technology which enables them to

cultivate crops indigenous to their diets. (Food ladder: Report).

To promote gender equality and sustainable development efforts are being made in an integrated and holistic manner to facilitate more sustainable and inclusive growth in economy and therefore not only the political economic legal framework but also the NGOs civil society and private sectors need to participate hand-in-hand. There are a few examples of such a case and there are many more all around The World gender responsive budgeting can help ensure more equitable and effective resource allocation of resources that would faster distributional outcomes in favour of gender equality. At global level there is a need for an agreement of indicators on sustainable development and economic growth which measures gender equality and women's empowerment and participation.

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